

Supplementary Material: Surveys

Pre-Simulation Survey: FELLOW

1. Age _____
2. Years in fellowship _____
3. Number of hours per *year* spent in participating in simulation team training in your institution as a learner _____ hours
4. Number of hours per *year* spent in teaching via simulation team training in your institution as simulation faculty _____ hours
5. Number of hours per *year* spent participating in standardized patient-based simulation training (excluding OSCE) in your institution as a learner _____ hours
6. Number of hours per *year* spent teaching in standardized patient-based simulation training (excluding OSCE) in your institution as a learner _____ hours
7. Do you believe that simulation training is an essential part of clinical practice? YES/
NO
8. Do you believe that simulation training is an important part of patient safety? YES/
NO
9. Do you think simulation team training should be part of AAGL MIGS' fellow
Bootcamp? YES/ NO
10. Do you think simulation team training should be part of the fellowship curriculum in
your institution? YES/ NO
11. Do you desire to learn more about simulation training and simulation-based
curriculum development? YES/ NO
12. Would you attend a post-graduate course or round table discussion at the AAGL
annual meeting regarding simulation training and simulation-based curriculum
development? YES/ NO

If yes, what topics would interest you most at such a course (Circle all that apply):

- a. Developing a simulation scenario/case
- b. Understanding available technology for simulation
- c. Debriefing techniques

Post-Simulation Survey: FELLOW

Please use the below scale to answer the following questions:

1-strongly disagree; 2-disagree; 3-neutral; 4-agree; 5-strongly agree

1. The faculty clearly communicated the objectives of the simulation scenarios.
1 2 3 4 5
2. The faculty supported a safe learning environment that encouraged active learning.
1 2 3 4 5
3. The knowledge gained through the simulation experience can be transferred to the clinical setting.
1 2 3 4 5
4. The simulation scenarios allowed me to use critical-thinking skills.
1 2 3 4 5
5. The faculty provided constructive feedback and encouraged discussion after the simulation scenarios.
1 2 3 4 5
6. I have more confidence in responding to a critical event in the future.
1 2 3 4 5
7. I have learned techniques to communicate more effectively during a critical event.
1 2 3 4 5
8. The major vascular injury session has given me confidence in managing intraoperative hemorrhage.
1 2 3 4 5
9. I recommend that the AAGL Bootcamp include such simulation sessions in future programs.
1 2 3 4 5
10. Topic and content covered in this session were relevant to my training and clinical practice.
1 2 3 4 5
11. Format (simulation, hands-on skills) was appropriate for the content.
1 2 3 4 5

Please answer the following 2 questions with the following scale

1 - not prepared; 2 - minimally prepared; 3 - moderately prepared; 4 - very prepared

12. How prepared did you feel for managing an intraoperative hemorrhage PRIOR to this session?

1 2 3 4
13. How prepared do you feel for managing an intraoperative hemorrhage AFTER this session?

1 2 3 4

14. Please provide us with topics you think should be included in simulation sessions in the future:

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS:

Please tell us how to improve; what worked well, and you think needs to be changed. We make changes to the programs based on what you say!

Pre-Simulation Survey: FACULTY

1. Age _____
2. Years in practice _____
3. Number of hours per *year* spent in participating in simulation team training in your institution as a learner _____ hours
4. Number of hours per *year* spent in teaching via simulation team training in your institution as simulation faculty _____ hour
5. Number of hours per *year* spent participating in standardized patient-based simulation training (excluding OSCE) in your institution as a learner _____ hours
6. Number of hours per *year* spent teaching in standardized patient-based simulation training (excluding OSCE) in your institution as a learner _____ hours
7. Do you believe that simulation training is an essential part of clinical practice? YES/ NO
8. Do you believe that simulation training is an important part of patient safety? YES/ NO
9. Do you think simulation team training should be part of AAGL MIGS' fellow Bootcamp? YES/ NO
10. Do you think simulation team training should be part of the fellowship curriculum in your institution? YES/ NO
11. Do you desire to learn more about simulation training and simulation-based curriculum development? YES/ NO
12. Would you attend a post-graduate course or round table discussion at the AAGL annual meeting regarding simulation training and simulation-based curriculum development? YES/ NO

If yes, what topics would interest you most at such a course (circle all that apply):

- a. Developing a simulation scenario/case
- b. Understanding available technology for simulation
- c. Debriefing techniques
- d. Evaluation of trainees/students

Post-Simulation Survey: FACULTY

1. Do you believe that simulation training is an essential part of clinical practice? YES/
NO
2. Do you believe that simulation training is an important part of patient safety? YES/
NO
3. Do you think simulation team training should be part of AAGL MIGS' fellow
Bootcamp? YES/ NO
4. Do you think simulation team training should be part of the fellowship curriculum in
your institution? YES/ NO
5. Do you desire to learn more about simulation training and simulation-based
curriculum development? YES/ NO
6. Would you attend a post-graduate course or round table discussion at the AAGL
annual meeting regarding simulation training and simulation-based curriculum
development? YES/ NO

If yes, what topics would interest you most at such a course (circle all that apply):

- a. Developing a simulation scenario/case
- b. Understanding available technology for simulation
- c. Debriefing techniques
- d. Evaluation of trainees/students